

Grant code	
Title	Improving post-trial access arrangements in clinical trials in Sub-Saharan Africa
Grant agreement number	CSA2019ERC-2680

Deliverable number	D5.9.
Deliverable name	(Publication on) PTA trends
Deliverable type	R
Organisation and person responsible	Ewanat Gebrehanna, SPHMMC
Dissemination level	Public
Contractual delivery date (month)	M26
Actual delivery date (month)	M39
Version	1.0
Total number of pages	

This activity is part of the EDCTP2 programme supported by the European Union (grant number CSA2019ERC-2680 AccessAfrica).

Patterns of Post-Trial Access in Sub-Saharan Africa: Results from Work Package 2 of Access-Africa Project

This report presents the findings of work package 2 of Access-Africa project, which aimed to understand the patterns and requirements of post-trial access (PTA) in sub-Saharan Africa countries. PTA refers to the provision of continued access to beneficial interventions or products that have been tested in clinical trials for the trial participants and/or the host communities after the trial ends. PTA is an ethical obligation for researchers and sponsors, as well as a human right for trial participants and communities.

The report is based on four methods: review of published trial protocols, online survey of principal investigators (PIs), co-investigators (Co-PIs) and sponsors, interviews with institutional review board (IRB) members and PIs/Co-PIs, and desk review of research ethics guidelines and articles. The methods were applied to clinical trials conducted in sub-Saharan Africa between 2007 and 2009 on tuberculosis, malaria and neglected tropical diseases. The report summarizes the key findings, challenges and recommendations for improving PTA practices and policies in the region.

Review of published trial protocols

The first method involved searching and identifying published trial protocols from two well-recognized clinical trial registries: the Pan African Clinical Trials Registry (PACTR) and Clinicaltrials.gov. The search criteria were trials done on tuberculosis, malaria and neglected tropical diseases and those that have been conducted between 2007 and 2009. Most of the protocols from the two websites lacked mandatory information that informed about their post-trial arrangements and practices. Only 10 protocols had the required information.

Online survey of PIs, Co-PIs and sponsors

The second method involved preparing an online survey and sending out emails to the list of contacts for PIs, Co-PIs and sponsors. The list was obtained from the clinical trial registry websites. The online survey was prepared on REDcap and a link to the survey was sent out to more than 300 eligible individuals. Individuals were also contacted through their Twitter and LinkedIn pages. The response rate was very low, only 40 individuals responded to the survey. About half of the respondents reported having arranged a PTA.

Interviews with IRB members and PIs/Co-PIs

The third method involved inviting IRB members, PIs and Co-PIs for interviews. The interviewees were selected based on the list of contacts from different sites that had information on IRB membership.

Interviews were conducted with IRB members from Ethiopia, Kenya, Tanzania, Rwanda and Ghana. Two PIs were interviewed from Ethiopia. Except for the Ghana IRB member interview, all the interviews were transcribed and key information were summarized.

Desk review of research ethics guidelines and articles

The fourth method involved conducting a desk review of research ethics guidelines and published articles on research ethics in sub-Saharan countries. This method was included to supplement the information obtained from the other methods and gain an objective perspective of the availability of PTA in regulatory and implementation documents. The documents collected included research ethics guidelines and published articles on research ethics in sub-Saharan countries.

Key findings

The key findings from the four methods are as follows:

- There is a varied level of understanding of what PTA is by IRB and PI members from different African countries. During interviews, most of the respondents interpreted PTA as making data, findings and publications available to the community and concerned bodies. Availing products like drugs were mentioned but with reservation of feasibility of implementation.
- In some countries, like Rwanda, including PTA is not mandatory during protocol review and the option is left for the researcher and funder. In Ethiopia, clinical researchers are not requested to present their PTA plans during protocol review. IRB members from Ethiopia who participated in our study believe that the responsibility of providing post-trial access should be that of the local government and stakeholders working in the health field. Besides, some argue that it is not relevant to ask PTA at the protocol review stage as the outcome of the trials cannot be 'predicted'.
- IRB board members from Tanzania stated that PTA is not something that is requested during clinical protocol review process. This is in line with the 2009 Tanzania Ethics guideline that explicitly requires researchers to make data and publications available at the end of trial. However, there is nothing mentioned about post-trial access.
- The Kenya biomedical research ethics guideline clearly demands PTA ahead of protocol approval. It states that "sponsoring agency should agree in advance of the research that any product developed through this research will be made reasonably available to the inhabitants of the community in which research has been conducted or to the whole country at the completion of successful testing". However, even though Kenya has a clear demand for PTA, IRB members believe that it is a challenge to enforce implementation. There is no legal framework to settle disputes at global level if an external sponsor of clinical trial refuses to honor their promise in the protocol.
- Nigeria has a dedicated legislation for clinical trial regulation. This legislation has details on the requirements for the registration, conduct and regulation of trials. It has put dedicated articles on good clinical practice for clinical trials. However, it does not have a specific request or recommendation for post-trial access.
- The South Africa Health Products Regulatory Authority's demand for trial registration does not include post-trial provision requirements. It gives emphasis on good clinical practice guideline, which ensures safety of participants during clinical trial.

Challenges of PTA

The challenges of PTA identified from the study are as follows:

- There is a gap in understanding what PTA should include by regulatory bodies and research ethics committees. The fact that some of the respondents in this study were not clear about the concept and who should be responsible is the highlight of the gap.
- The fear of pushing away clinical trials from being conducted in certain countries is used as a reasonable argument by sponsors and researchers. One of the key arguments is that providing PTA will make research costly and thus less frequent. Developing countries may fear driving away researchers and sponsors from their territory if they have 'high' demand for PTA.
- The lack of legally binding platform at international level plays a critical role in the lack of PTA. There is no legal entity or framework that addresses the issue if sponsors refuse to implement the post-trial access agreement that was put in the protocol. Even countries like Kenya who have a mandatory demand for PTA strategy lack such enforcement.

Conclusion

The study reveals that PTA is a neglected and misunderstood issue in sub-Saharan Africa. Most countries have not included PTA as part of their health research ethics guidelines, making implementation challenging. There is also a lack of awareness and capacity among researchers, sponsors and IRBs to plan and execute PTA. The existing international and national policies and guidelines are insufficient and inconsistent to ensure PTA. There is a need for more advocacy, education and collaboration among stakeholders to improve PTA practices and policies in the region.

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